

Do the Trainees of Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira Really Improve in Teaching Aptitude after Receiving Training?

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ABSTRACT : Teacher training programme has an effective value to increase teaching aptitude among school teachers. The present study was conducted to inquire the improvement of teaching aptitude among the trainees who received training programme in the session 2012-13 from Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira (CTE). DSTAT was administered twice (before and after receiving the training programme) on 102 randomly selected trainees for measuring their teaching aptitude. The major finding was observed that trainees improved significantly in teaching aptitude with respect to all categorical variables under consideration. It was concluded from this study that Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira (CTE), as a college of teacher education is executing such duties over the years to the extent that improves the teaching aptitude of trainees by providing successful and effective training programme.

Keywords : Teacher education, teaching aptitude, training.

Introduction

An educational institution performs a significant function of providing learning experiences to lead their students from the darkness of ignorance to the light of knowledge. The key personnel in the institutions who play

an important role to bring about this transformation are teachers. As stated by NCTE (1998) in Quality Concerns in Secondary Teacher Education, "The teacher is the most important element in any educational program. It is the teacher who is mainly responsible for

implementation of the educational process at any stage.” The National Curriculum Framework, 2005 places demands and expectations on the teacher, which need to be addressed by both initial and continuing teacher education. A teacher with a high teaching aptitude can execute the task of teaching better than a person with low aptitude. According to Bingham (1937), Aptitude refers to those qualities characterizing person’s ways of behavior which is serve to indicate how well he can learn to meet and solve certain specific kinds of problem. Teaching aptitude as stated by Dhiya & Singh (?) is “...a condition or set of characteristics including knowledge, understanding and attitude regarded as symptomatic or indicative of individual’s ability to acquire with training abilities for teaching work”. According to Rao (1990), “Aptitude is a psychological potentiality of a specific nature or character which, with necessary and appropriate training, helps brining about improvement in the performance of that particular type” (p-353). The teaching aptitude of a teacher can also be improved if proper training is given to him as suggested by Rao. Banerjee’s (1956) study on the inter-relation of two aspects of training viz., practice teaching and theoretical studies with general intelligence and teaching aptitude found positive correlation between these variables. Sharma (1971) found that, besides other variables such as academic grades, socio- economic status, teaching experience, teaching aptitude is also a predictor of teacher effectiveness.

Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math, Howrah, the sole NAAC accredited A⁺ and an autonomous teacher education college in West Bengal provides education and training (B.Ed) to the teachers of secondary stages in

West Bengal with the expectation to improve its trainees teaching aptitude so that after passing out from this institution, trainees can perform better. It is obvious that the quality of education is increasingly judged by focusing on pupil performance, what pupils actually learn, and how well they learn it. Improvement in teaching aptitude of trainees might be an indicator of the training being given by this institute with respect to the curriculum content and its transaction. The present researchers undertook the study to inquire about whether the trainees really improve in their teaching aptitude after receiving training from Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira.

Objective of the Study

- To study whether there was any improvement in teaching aptitude of trainees after training.
- To study whether there was any improvement in teaching aptitude of deputed (who are already teachers in secondary schools) trainees after training.
- To study whether there was any improvement in teaching aptitude of fresher trainees after training
- To study whether there was any improvement in teaching aptitude of trainees of arts discipline after training
- To study whether there was any improvement in teaching aptitude of trainees of science discipline after training.

Hypothesis

For this study following null hypotheses were framed:

H₀1: There was no significant difference in teaching aptitude of trainees before and after training.

H₀2: There was no significant difference in teaching aptitude of deputed trainees before and after training

H₀3: There was no significant difference in teaching aptitude of fresher trainees before and after training.

H₀4: There was no significant difference in teaching aptitude of trainees of arts discipline before and after training.

H₀5: There was no significant difference in teaching aptitude of trainees of science discipline before and after training.

Methodology of the Study

Sample:

102 trainees who took admission to the B.Ed course in the session 2012-13 were selected randomly as sample.

Tools:

Dahiya & Singh Teaching Aptitude Test (DSTAT) was used in this study for measuring teaching aptitude of the sample. The test consist 50 items. Each item has four multiple choice answers among which one is correct. Each correct answer bears score 1 (one), thus maximum possible score, one can obtain is 50 as raw score. The raw scores can be

transformed into standard score according to the norms given in the test.

Reliability and Validity of the Tools

Reliability of the test was calculated by Split-half method (using even and odd items). The reliability coefficient $r = 0.828$. The factorial validity was calculated. Inter-correlations matrix (50 x 50) was factor analysed using principal Component Analysis Extraction Method and Quartimax with Kaiser Normalization Rotation Method. Five major factors were extracted accounting for 69.45% of the total variance.

Method of Data Collection

DSTAT was administered twice to the sample, first administration was done within one month of the commencement of the training course and second administration was done on the last day of the course. Two sets of scores were received and recorded as pre training score and post training score respectively.

Techniques of Analysis

The collected data were analyzed through SPSS 19.0 version. The Statistics such as Mean, SD, and 'Z' values were calculated in this study and the significance of 'Z' values were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results & Data Interpretations

The results of the study are presented in the following tables :

Table 1: Sample Frame:

Deputed Trainee (N=49)		Fresher Trainee Student teacher (N= 53)		TOTAL
Arts	Science	Arts	Science	N=102
30	19	38	15	

Table 2: Group Statistics Report

	PRE TRAINING SCORE	POST TRAINING SCORE
N	102	102
Mean	43.4966	53.9698
Std. Deviation	12.23538	4.58688

Table 3: Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
PRE-TRAINING SCORE	.132	102	.000	.929	102	.000
POST-TRAINING SCORE	.110	102	.004	.950	102	.001

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

After testing the normality of scores, (From Table no. 3) it was found that scores before training (pre-training) and after training (post-training) both are non normal in nature as the 'p' value yielded in Shapiro-Wilk test of normality are 0.000 and 0.001(both are less than 0.05) respectively. So it was decided to test the null hypotheses through non-parametric tests (Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test).

Testing of Hypotheses

Testing of H_0 1

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test for all trainees

Table 5- Test Statistics^b

	POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE
Z	-6.054 ^a
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

a. Based on negative ranks.

b. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

A Wilcoxon Signed Rank test was conducted to evaluate whether all trainees have improved in their teaching aptitude after receiving training. The results (from Table no. 5) indicate a

Table no. 4. Ranks

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE	Negative Ranks	26 ^a	31.29	813.50
	Positive Ranks	76 ^b	58.41	4439.50
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	102		

a. POST TRAINING SCORE < PRE TRAINING SCORE

b. POST TRAINING SCORE > PRE TRAINING SCORE

c. POST TRAINING SCORE = PRE TRAINING SCORE

significant difference, $z = -6.054$, $p = 0.000$ ($p < .05$). Hence, the null hypothesis, $H_0 1$ is rejected and it can be safely said that trainees improve in their teaching aptitude after receiving the teacher training.

Testing of $H_0 2$:

Table : 6- Ranks^d

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE	Negative Ranks	18 ^a	20.64	371.50
	Positive Ranks	31 ^b	27.53	853.50
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	49		

a. POST TRAINING SCORE < PRE TRAINING SCORE

b. POST TRAINING SCORE > PRE TRAINING SCORE

c. POST TRAINING SCORE = PRE TRAINING SCORE

d. CATEGORY = DEPUTED

Table: 7- Test Statistics^{b,c}

	POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE
Z	-2.399 ^a
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.016

a. Based on negative ranks.

b. CATEGORY = DEPUTED

c. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test

The results (Table no. 7) shows that $z = -2.399$, p value is 0.016 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis, $H_0 2$ is rejected and it can be said that significant difference exists between the score of pre training and post training. So, it is interpreted that deputed students improved in teaching aptitude after receiving the training.

Testing of $H_0 3$:

Table: 8- Ranks^d

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE	Negative Ranks	8 ^a	11.25	90.00
	Positive Ranks	45 ^b	29.80	1341.00
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	53		

- a. POST TRAINING SCORE < PRE TRAINING SCORE
- b. POST TRAINING SCORE > PRE TRAINING SCORE
- c. POST TRAINING SCORE = PRE TRAINING SCORE
- d. CATEGORY = FRESHER

Table 9. - Test Statistics^{b,c}

	POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE
Z	-5.538 ^a
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
a. Based on negative ranks. b. CATEGORY = FRESHER c. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test	

The results (Table no. 9) shows that $z = -5.538$, p value is 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Hence, the null hypothesis, $H_0 3$ is rejected and it is interpreted that fresher trainees improved in teaching aptitude after receiving the training programme.

Testing of $H_0 4$:

Table 10- Ranks^d

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE	Negative Ranks	19a	22.95	436.00
	Positive Ranks	49b	38.98	1910.00
	Ties	0c		
	Total	68		
a. POST TRAINING SCORE < PRE TRAINING SCORE b. POST TRAINING SCORE > PRE TRAINING SCORE c. POST TRAINING SCORE = PRE TRAINING SCORE d. DISCIPLINE = ARTS				

Table 11- Test Statistics^{b,c}

	POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE
Z	-4.505 ^a
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
a. Based on negative ranks.	b. DISCIPLINE = ARTS
c. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test	

In Case of trainees of arts discipline, he results (Table no. 11) shows that the $z = -4.505$, p value is 0.000 ($p < .05$). Hence, the null hypothesis, H_04 is rejected and it is concluded that trainees of arts discipline improved in teaching aptitude after receiving the training.

Testing of H_05 :

Table 12. - Ranks^d

		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE	Negative Ranks	7 ^a	8.86	62.00
	Positive Ranks	27 ^b	19.74	533.00
	Ties	0 ^c		
	Total	34		
a. POST TRAINING SCORE < PRE TRAINING SCORE b. POST TRAINING SCORE > PRE TRAINING SCORE c. POST TRAINING SCORE = PRE TRAINING SCORE d. DISCIPLINE = SCIENCE				

Table 13. - Test Statistics^{b,c}

	POST TRAINING SCORE - PRE TRAINING SCORE
Z	-4.027 ^a
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
a. Based on negative ranks. b. DISCIPLINE = SCIENCE c. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test	

The results (Table no. 13) of trainees of science discipline indicates that $z = -4.027$, p value is 0.000 ($p < .05$). Hence, the null hypothesis, H_05 is rejected; it is can be said that trainees of science discipline improved in teaching aptitude after receiving the training.

Conclusion

The job of teaching requires constant search for updated knowledge, latest information, improvement of aptitude and skills. Teacher

education is the component of any educational system which provides education and training to the teachers to acquire the competencies and skills of teaching for the improvement in the quality of teachers.

It was found from the study that after receiving the training programme, the teaching aptitude was improved in all groups of trainees such as deputed, fresher, arts and science discipline. So, the impact of training on the trainees can be mentionable and satisfactory.

Insignificantly and undesirably few trainees' post training score is lower than the pre training score; it implies that effect of training on them was negative. With the help of telephonic interview and face to face interview, the researchers tried to understand the causes of negative impact over them and it was found that negligence by the trainees, inattentiveness, absence, feeling of less interest and casual approach to training classes might be the probable causes of the negative impact over them. Furthermore, rigorous qualitative study can be conducted to identify genuine causes lying with the training programme or the trainees.

Discussion

Pre-service training (B.Ed) is the training provided before employment of teachers and is generally a pre requisite for getting the job of teaching. It is aimed at professional growth of the teacher and is planned and provided in such a way that it leads to the development in him a positive attitude and aptitude towards education and towards improving his own performance in terms of better student learning. Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, as a college of teacher education is executing such duties over the years which makes the institution as a NAAC accredited A+ grade and autonomous college of teacher education. But there should not be any scope of self contentment because it will inhibit the intention and endeavor of further development of the institution. Moreover, tireless effort for progress can help this institution to contribute a lot to the field of education.

Limitations

No study is flawless. This study has its limitations. It would be much better if all the

trainees could be selected as population of the study. The Bengali adaptation DSTAT could be used for the testing of teaching aptitude.

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